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Research Article

Study Of Antibacterial Activity & Phytochemical Test Of *Thuja Occidentalis* Root L. (Cupressaceae)

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ABSTRACT

Thuja occidentalis (commonly morpankhi) is a genus of coniferous tree in the cupressaceae (cypress family). In this study, Thuja root were collected from local area sarojini nagar, and dried under tray dryer for 10 days. They were then grinded using mechanical grinder and extracted with a Soxhlet extractor in two solvent systems, i.e. (F1) ethyl acetate: acetone: ethanol (40:30:30) and (F2) methanol: distilled water (70:30). This study conferred the screening of phytochemical constituents. This study examined the antibacterial activity of Thuja roots extract on gram positive (*Staphylococcus aureus* and *enterococcus faecalis* and *bacillus subtilis*.) and gram-negative bacteria (*E. coli*). Root extract was obtained by soxhlet extraction technique using mixture of Ethyl acetate, acetone, ethanol (non aqueous Extract) ratio 40:30:30 and methanol, water (aqueous extract) ratio 70:30 as the solvent. The antibacterial activity of *Thuja occidentalis* was tested. Standardization of crude drugs extracted from plants plays a vital role in identifying the quality and purity of medications. Current research analysis reveals standardization of crude drugs that includes moisture content, acid-insoluble and water-soluble, and different soluble extraction values were estimated. The highest extractive values were recorded for the water-soluble extract of crude drugs, bioactive substances present in medicinal plants that can lead to drug discovery and development. The present study deals with the phytochemical components of the medicinal plant *Thuja occidentalis* from the Cupressaceae family in order to relate their presence to the bioactivity of the plants. Current research highlights that methanolic extracts of *Thuja occidentalis* had the highest number of phytochemicals compared to other solvent extracts. Therefore, methanolic extracts of *Thuja occidentalis* have the most significant potential to treat various human diseases and have profound medical utility.

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INTRODUCTION

Thuja occidentalis (commonly Morpankhi, Cupressaceae) is a dioeciously evergreen tree or shrub that has been employed for a number of antipyretic, antitussive, astringent, diuretic, cooling, and stomach functions. The phytochemicals labdane and isopimarane, as well as monoterpenoids and sesquiterpenoids found in the essential oils of various plant components, were isolated from various portions of *Platyclusus orientalis*. Two monoglycerol derivatives derived from pollen and two diterpenoids from pericarp and leaves. The most advantageous elements of *T. orientalis* oil are camphor, fenchone, isothujone, and thujone. Treatments using a variety of complementary therapies are gaining popularity. The use of plants to treat a variety of illnesses is important in this setting. Despite being widely

utilised around the world, several governments do not formally recognise folk treatments. More than 80% of people in Asia and Africa utilize plant extracts to treat a range of diseases.

Figure:-1 Plant of *Thuja occidentalis*

Plant Description:-	
Family	Cupressaceae
Synonym	Tree of Life, Yellow Cedar, American Arborvitae
Genus	<i>Thuja</i>
Species :	<i>T. occidentalis</i>
Botanical Source	<i>Thuja occidentalis</i>
Active Constituents	Flavonoids, Thujone is the primary component of the volatile (0.4–1%) essential oil, accounting for up to 65% of the total oil, along with alpha-pinene, camphor, borneol, and fenchone. Sesquiterpenes, flavonoids, and polysaccharides are other constituents

Plant part description:-

Tree:-

The tree is modest and slow-growing, reaching a height of 15-20 m (49-66 ft) with a trunk diameter of 0.5 m (1 ft 8 in). On rare occasions, older trees can reach heights of 30 m (98 ft) and diameters of 2 m (6 ft 7 in). An evergreen tree is *Thuja orientalis*. Hardy *Thuja orientalis* is a small to medium-sized tree that typically does not exceed a height of 20 meters.

Seed cones:-

The narrow, yellow-green, developing to brown seed cones measure 9–14 mm in length, 4-5 mm in width, and have six to eight overlapping scales. About eight seeds are included in each. The male

cones are tiny, barely noticeable, and found at the ends of twigs. When mature, female cones have lengths of about 1 to 2 cm and open in the first year, at 6 to 8 months of age.

Leaves:-

The leaves of Hardy *Thuja orientalis* are predominantly scale-like, ranging in length from 1 to 10 mm, except for the tiny seedlings in their first year, which have needle-like leaves. These scale leaves are arranged in four rows along the branches, alternating in decussate pairs. The leaves have a rough texture, with a lighter color on the lower surface and a darker color on the upper surface. During winter, the leaves may acquire a coppery tint. They are arranged in flattened, fan-

shaped clusters in four rows, and resin glands are grouped oppositely within these clusters.

Bark:-

Reddish-brown in colour, it has ridges and peels off in long, slender strips. Evergreen thuja trees range in height from 10 to 200 feet (3 to 61 metres) and have reddish-brown, fibrous-textured bark. The shoots of Hardy Thuja orientalis are flat and typically have only one plane of side shoots. This

means that the side shoots emerge from the main shoot in a single plane, rather than being arranged in multiple planes or directions. This gives the shoots a relatively flat appearance.

Roots:-

Small trees' roots can reach a depth of up to 8 inches, whereas the roots of larger trees can extend as far as 18 to 24 inches. They need direct sunlight, but they can also grow in dark environments.

**Figure 2:- Thuja occidentalis plant part: A) Thuja tree B) Leaves C) Seeds con D) Bark E) Root
A comparison of T. occidentalis's bioactive potential with those of other species in the Thuja genus.**

Thuja species	Beneficial Effects Based on Biological Activities	
	Medicinal uses	Industrial uses
T. koraiensis	antimicrobial, antioxidant	---
T. occidentalis	antimicrobial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antitumor, hepatoprotective, gastroprotective, antidiabetic, antiatherosclerotic, radioprotective, antipyretic	antifungal agent for biocontamination
T. plicata	antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory and tissue remodeling	antimicrobial agents for decontamination of building
T. standishii	antimicrobial, antitumor	
T. sutchuenensis	Antimicrobial	

General uses of the plant:-

- It is traditionally used to cure coughs.
- Like many other members of the Cupressaceae family, Thuja can cause allergic reactions that include breathing issues, skin and eye.
- The plant has been extensively studied and shown to possess various beneficial properties, such as anti-epileptic, antiviral, antiallergic, antibacterial, antioxidant, and hair-growth-promoting effects.
- Scalds and burns can be treated with the root and bark.
- The leaves are used to treat a variety of ailments, including those that are antibacterial, astringent, antipyretic, stomachic, antitussive, antipyretic and diuretic.
- The usage of trees in general for various medicinal products and aromatherapy concoctions dates back a long way
- It has been used externally to cure fungal skin illnesses including ringworm and thrush, reduce the discomfort associated with arthritis and rheumatism, and eradicate anal or vaginal warts.
- The tree is known as arbour vitae or the "tree of life" because of its vitamin C-rich leaves and twigs, which are beneficial in preventing or treating scurvy.

Biological activities

Anti-Inflammatory Activity

Inflammation is an essential defence mechanism that occurs in response to tissue damage, aimed at facilitating tissue repair. The activation of macrophages is initiated through neutrophil extravasation within the capillary network, leading to the production of various proinflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α , interleukins, and interferons, which play crucial roles in regulating inflammatory responses. Although limited, there have been some studies investigating the anti-

inflammatory properties of components found in *T. occidentalis*.

Antifungal Activity

In a recent study, the essential oil from *Thuja occidentalis* leaves and cones showed antibacterial efficacy against yeast like *Candida albicans*, fungus like *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus niger*, and Gram-positive bacteria like *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Listeria monocytogenes*. Gram-negative microorganisms including *Aeromonas hydrophila*, *Salmonella typhimurium*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Pseudomonas*. Antifungal properties may be found in essential oils.

Antiviral Activity

It has been demonstrated that *T. occidentalis* polysaccharides contain antiviral and immune-stimulating qualities, with the capacity to lessen HIV-1 and influenza. A. At a concentration of 625 g/mL, thuja polysaccharides (TPS) suppressed HIV. It was demonstrated that freshly infected MT-2 cells had no detrimental effects on MT-4 cells and displayed lower expression of the HIV-1 specific antigen. emphasised the effect of *T. occidentalis*' high-molecular-weight polysaccharide on HIV-1. An in vitro study found that an isolated *T. occidentalis* component increased the number of cells making antibodies.

Hair growth promoting activity

In East Asia, *T. orientalis* has long been used to treat people who have baldness and hair loss. According to Zhang et al.'s research, *T. orientalis* hot water extract stimulated the anagen phase in telogenic C57BL/6 N mice, promoting hair growth. In contrast to either the control group or the group given 1% minoxidil, topical treatment of *T. orientalis* extract generated an earlier anagen phase and prolonged the mature anagen phase.

Antimicrobial activity:

The essential oil from the seed coats of *T. orientalis* against six bacterial pathogens, including *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus*

fumigatus, *Rhizopus oryzae*, *Fusarium psidi*, and *Curvularia lunata*, as well as five fungal pathogens. The oil had good to moderate action against each of the six test microorganisms. The monoterpene ketones α - and β -thujone, fenchone and sabinene, as well as the diterpenes beyerene and rimuene, were the predominant components in all samples. *S. aureus*, *S. epidermidis*, *P. aeruginosa*, *E. cloacae*, *K. pneumoniae*, *E. coli*, *Candida albicans*, *C. tropicalis*, and *C. glabrata* were tested for essential oil's antimicrobial activity. Thuja leaf essential oil's antibacterial properties were investigated by Malik and Singh 28 against microorganisms isolated from urinary tract infections. While *E. coli* was discovered to be a resistant bacteria, *P. mirabilis* and *S. aureus* were determined to be the most susceptible bacteria.

Antibacterial activity:

Antimicrobial substances can be found in essential oils, which are helpful sources. It is commonly known that plants contain antibacterial elements since these elements have served as a source of inspiration for new medication compounds used in herbal remedies for human health. *T. orientalis* contains large amounts of alpha, beta, and gamma thujaplicin, which may have the ability to chelate *Solmonella typhimurium* at low doses. *Streptococcus mutans* was resistant to the antibacterial effects of *T. orientalis*, according to Chen and colleagues. The antibacterial and antifungal effects of *Vernonia anthelmintica*, *Dryopteris chrysocoma*, and *Trachyspermum ammi* were tested in vitro on *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Yersinia aldovae*, *Citrobacter*, *Shigella flexneri*, *E. coli*, and *Staphylococcus aureus* in the alcohol concentrate made from *Thuja occidentalis* twigs. Antibacterial testing was done on six microscopic species, including *Citrobacter*, *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Yersinia aldovae*, *Shigella flexenari*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* all shown strong movement against all

bacteria. These concentrations were tested for their antifungal efficacy against six growths: *Candida albicans*, *Saccharomyces cereviciae*, *Aspergillus parasiticus*, *Trichophyton rubrum*, *Macrophomina*, and *Fusarium solani*. When used against several parasite strains, the concentrates demonstrated important results.

MATERIALS & METHOD

Cultivation Collection

Thuja is cultivated outdoors in a cool, humid microclimate in hedges, open ground, pots, solitary and group plantings, and forest protection strips. In November or March, these plants are set in place permanently. They favour soil that is deep, slightly damp, and well-drained. Thuja is cultivated for hedges with a 60–70 cm spacing between plants. Use a peat substrate, fertile ground, and organic fertilisers in the amount of 30–50 g per bucket of soil for growing it in pots or flower beds. Practise liquid top dressing with mineral fertilisers beginning in the second year of life. *Thuja occidentalis* fresh roots were gathered from locations in and around Lucknow. The gathered roots were cleaned and then chopped into little pieces so they could be turned into powder. To make powder, little bits of root were smashed in a mortar and pestle. *Thuja occidentalis* root powder was sieved through a 40-mesh sieve to obtain a fine powdered medication.

Morphology of Thuja occidentalis roots

Colour	Brownish colour
Oduor	pleasant and aromatic smell
Taste	Bitter/ tea like taste
Shape	Shape shallow and irregular
Size	25cm length
Texture	stringy

Figure 3:- Macroscopy of Thuja occidentalis roots
Microscopic of Thuja occidentalis

- Outermost layer of the circular roots is thick walled epiblema with many root hairs.
- Epiblema is followed by many layers of parenchymatous cortex.
- Inner to the cortex is present a layer of endodermis and many layers of pericycle.
- Vascular bundles are radially arranged and diarch to tetrarch with exarch protoxylem.
- Protoxylem is bifurcated (Y- shaped) towards the periphery, and in between each bifurcation is present a resin canal.
- Pith is poorly-developed or absent.

Drying and Powdering of Thuja occidentalis root

After cutting the roots into small pieces, it was washed, then the roots were dried at 100 OC temperature for two weeks, and then fine particles help with a motor pestle, it was converted into fine powder, then that powder was grinded in a mixer and that grinder powder was passed through a 40 no Sieve filter it and collect the powdered drug and the drug is ready.

(A)

(B)

(C)

Figure 4:-

A) Grinder

B) Sieving

C) Fine powder

Selection of solvents

Solvents are playing the major role in extraction process. There are two type solvent used in the extraction process non-aqueous solution not

present in water (ethyl acetate, acetone, ethanol) and Aqueous solution it means present in water (methanol, water). Based on the active constituents of *Thuja occidentalis*, solvents like -

- Ethyl acetate
- Acetone
- Ethanol
- Methanol
- Water

Figure 5:

A) Ethyl acetate: acetone: ethanol

B) Methanol: Water

Extraction by Soxhlation

On a small scale, the soxhlet device is utilised for the extraction. A Soxhlet extractor, a flask and a reflux condenser make up this apparatus.

Figure 6:- Soxhlet apparatus

The thick tube of the extractor was filled with the coarsely ground *Thuja occidentalis* powder that was contained in the filter paper thimble. In the extraction process for the plant medicine, two solvents—a non-aqueous solution and an aqueous solution—were used: ethyl acetate, acetone, ethanol (F1), and methanol, water (F2). During this time, soluble constituents were removed as the solvent liquid level slowly rose. The liquid is siphoned into the flask when its level reaches the siphon's top. Repeating the previous procedure, a portion of the solvent from the solution was once more evaporated, leaving the contents in the flask itself. Additionally, an ethyl acetate and methanol extract was used to remove the entire plant's contents. The plant was then taken out of the thimble and dried outside. After the plant is prepared to be treated with ethanol to remove the active components from the plant, pet ether from the plant is removed. The flask containing the solvent ethanol was filled and heated. Up until the last solute was extracted, the same procedure was repeated repeatedly. To get rid of the solvent ethanol, the extractive liquid that included active ingredients was treated with a rotary film evaporator.

Figure 7:- Extraction process

Figure 8:- Extraction of plant drug F1 & F2

Phytochemical Analysis

Thuja occidentalis is analysed using phytochemistry to identify phytochemicals like alkaloids, glycosides, carbohydrates, saponin, flavonoids, and fixed oil.

Alkaloids

The extracts sample was treated with potassium bismuth iodide solution (Dragendorff's reagent). Formation of orange red precipitate indicated the presence of alkaloids.

Carbohydrates

Dissolved 2gm extracts in 5ml water and filter it with filter paper. The filtrate was then mixed with

concentration sulphuric acid and adds few drops of Molish's reagent. Indication of pink or violet colour shows the availability of carbohydrates.

Phenolic compound

Take 2ml extract dissolved in H₂O and add 3-4 drops of ferric chloride solution and indicated the bluish black colour shows availability of phenols.

Tannins test

Take 0.5gm of dried powdered and boiled 0.5gm sample in 20ml of water in a test tube and filter the above mixture. Add few drop of 0.1% ferric chloride and developed brownish green or blue black colour shows availability of tannins.

Flavonoids

Treat the extract with few drops of lead acetate solution. Flavonoids were present because yellow precipitate formed.

Glycosides

In the Keller- Killani test, 2 ml of plant extract solution was treated with 0.5 ml of glacial acetic acid solution containing 2-3 drops of ferric chloride. One millilitre of concentrated sulphuric acid was added to the test tube, and the presence of deep blue colour indicated the presence of cardiac glycosides.

Fixed oils and fats

One drop of concentrated sample was placed between two filter sheets and kept undisturbed for 2 minutes. Development of oil stains on paper shows presence of fat and oil

Saponins

2ml of the sample extract was mixed in 20ml of water and shake it in a graduated cylinder for 15 min. Emergence of 1 cm layer of foam shows the availability of saponin.

Figure 9: – Phytochemical test (Alkaloids, Glycosides, carbohydrates, phenolic compound, tannins, saponin)

ANTIBACTERIAL TEST PREPARATION

Antibacterial-Zone Inhibition Test- *B. Subtilis*

Disc Diffusion Method

Sample – F1

Amount present per disc in μg

Dispensed Volume- $10\mu\text{L}$

Positive Control- $10\mu\text{g}$

Figure:-10 Disc Diffusion Plate- Sample – F1

Sample – F2

Amount present per disc in μg
Dispensed Volume- $10\mu\text{L}$
Positive Control- $10\mu\text{g}$

Figure:-11 Disc Diffusion Plate- Sample – F2

Antibacterial -Zone Inhibition Test- E.coli
Disk Diffusion Method

Sample- F1

Amount present per Disk in μg
Dispensed Volume- $10\mu\text{L}$
Positive Control - $10\mu\text{g}$

Figure:- 12 Disc Diffusion Plate- Sample- F1

Sample- F2

A

B

C

Amount present per Disk in μg

Dispensed Volume- $10\mu\text{L}$

Positive Control - $10\mu\text{g}$

Figure:- 13 Disc Diffusion Plate- Sample- F2

Antibacterial-Zone Inhibition Test- S.aureus

Disk Diffusion Method

Sample- F1

A

B

C

Amount present per Disc in μg

Dispensed Volume- $10\mu\text{L}$

Positive Control - $10\mu\text{g}$

Figure:- 14 Disc Diffusion Plate- Sample- F1

Sample- F2

A

B

C

Amount present per Disc in μg

Dispensed Volume- $10\mu\text{L}$

Positive Control - $10\mu\text{g}$

Figure:-15 Disc Diffusion Plate- Sample- F2

Antibacterial-Zone Inhibition Test- P.aeruginosa

Disc Diffusion Method

Sample- F1

A

B

C

Amount present per Disc in μg

Dispensed Volume- $10\mu\text{L}$

Positive Control - $10\mu\text{g}$

Figure: - 16 Disc Diffusion Plate- Sample- F1

Disc Diffusion Method

Sample- F2

Amount present per Disc in μg
 Dispensed Volume- 10 μL
 Positive Control - 10 μg

Figure:-17 Disc Diffusion Plate- Sample- F2

RESULT

Final extract of *Thuja occidentalis*

The root extract of *Thuja occidentalis* was successfully accomplished by using Ethyl acetate, acetone, ethanol (F1) and methanol & water (F2) was using soxhlet extraction at 120 °C for 48 hrs. The detail of extraction process was described in above chapter. The prepared extracts were evaluated for several phytochemical characteristics, including Carbohydrate, Tannins, Phenolic compound, Fixed oil & fats, Glycosides, Saponin and the result of these tests showed in table no...and The root extract were further evaluated against various bacterial species such as *E. coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *B. Subtilis*. The result of anti-bacterial activity was discussed in bellowing.

Figure:-18

Phytochemical analysis of herbal extract:-

Table:-2 Phytochemical analysis

Name of test	<i>Thuja orientalis</i> (root)
Carbohydrate	+++
Tannins	+++
Flavanoids	---
Phenolic compound	+++
Fixed oil & fats	---
Glycosides	---
Saponin	---
Akaloids	---

Antibacterial activity – B. Subtilis F1

Table:-3 Anti- Bacterial Activity- B. Subtilis F1

Amount (µg/disk)	Plate A	Plate B	Plate C	Average	SD	SEM
PC	33	34	34	33.6667	0.57735	0.33333
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
62.5	8	5	5	6	1.73205	1
125	9	7	7	7.66667	1.1547	0.66667
250	10	9	10	9.66667	0.57735	0.33333
500	11	9	10	10	1	0.57735
1000	11	10	11	10.6667	0.57735	0.33333

Antibacterial Activity- B. subtilis- F1

Graph:-1 Anti- Bacterial Activity- B. Subtilis F1

Antibacterial bioassay – B. Subtilis F2

Table:-9 Anti- Bacterial Bioassay– P.aeruginosa F1

Amount (µg/disk)	Plate A	Plate B	Plate C	Average	SD	SEM
Pc	36	34	34	34.6667	1.1547	0.66667
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
31.25	5	5	5	5	0	0
62.5	6	7	7	6.66667	0.57735	0.33333
125	7	8	9	8	1	0.57735
250	8	9	10	9	1	0.57735
500	9	10	11	10	1	0.57735

Antibacterial Activity -*P. aeruginosa*- F1

Graph:-7 Anti- Bacterial Bioassay– P.aeruginosa F1

Antibacterial bioassay – P. Aeruginosa F2

Table:-10 Anti- Bacterial Bioassay– P. Aeruginosa F2

Amount (µg/disk)	Plate A	Plate B	Plate C	Average	SD	SEM
Pc	37	37	36	36.6667	0.57735	0.33333
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
31.25	5	5	5	5	0	0
62.5	7	7	6	6.66667	0.57735	0.33333
125	9	8	7	8	1	0.57735
250	10	10	8	9.33333	1.1547	0.66667
500	11	11	9	10.3333	1.1547	0.66667

Antibacterial Activity -*P. aeruginosa*- F2

Graph:-8 Anti- Bacterial Bioassay– P. Aeruginosa F2

CONCLUSION:

In this work has attempted to make herbal extract (F1 & F2) using Thuja occidentalis roots. The Non-aqueous soxhlet extract (F1) indicated the highest percentage yield (80%) and the aqueous soxhlet extract (F2) indicated the low percentage yield (76%) compare to F1. The root extract were evaluated against various bacterial species such as *E. coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *B. Subtilis* and the Result concluded that the all extract solution exhibited antibacterial effect and exhibited maximum activity with zones of inhibition from on *E. coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *B. Subtilis*. respectively. The generated extracts were further evaluated for several phytochemical characteristics, including Carbohydrate, Tannins, Phenolic compound, Fixed oil & fats, Glycosides, Saponin and the result of these tests showed in table no. According to literature survey the roots of *Thuja occidentalis* possess the necessary

medicinal characteristics and they utilized ethnobotanically and offer a lot of potential for creating antibiotics for bacterial illnesses. The herbal extract was developed by using an efficient, simple soxhlet extraction method with highest percentage yield ranging from 70-80% discussed in above paragraph. Literatures has already shown that plant extracts of *Thuja occidentalis* are not toxic to humans, Further study should focus on its use to treat bacterial infection in low- and middle-income nations, as well as the extraction method used for that purpose. Using the same conditions for all approaches and it is crucial to conduct experimental tests to confirm the efficacy of the *thuja occidentalis*. *Thuja* roots have been used to cure a variety of illnesses, the therapeutic uses of this plant may be connected to the discovery of bioactive substances. Thus, the result also concluded that the prepared extract has potential source for treating bacterial infections may be investigated that is:-

Table: 11 Bacterial infection and name

S. No.	Bacterial Name	Bacterial Infection
1.	E. coli	It can cause severe Foodborne disease. Ex:- Raw milk, Vegetable etc.

2.	Pseudomonas aeruginosa	It can cause infection in the blood, lungs or other parts of body after surgery.
3.	Staphylococcus aureus	It can cause Skin and Soft tissue infection such as furuncles, cellulitis and bloodstream, bone and joint infection also caused.
4.	Bacillus Subtilis	It can be infected bacteraemia, wound, burn, air and endocarditis etc.

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